

FitZone GYM Membership System: A Secure-by-Design Web Application Following the Secure Software Development Lifecycle

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Abstract—FitZone Gym Membership Management System is a secure-by-design web application, designed for the Secure Software Development (SWE 545) course. Using the system, the users can register, purchase or manage their gym membership in a secure environment. Three layers of protection against the most common online attacks — credential stuffing, SQL injection and payment manipulation. Based on the Secure Software Development Lifecycle (SSDLC) the system has been developed. After testing the results showed that all the 20 test cases of black boxes were passed for the four modules implemented, thus validating the security controls used.

Index Terms—SSDLC, Web Application Security, SQL Injection, Brute Force, Payment Validation, OWASP, Flask, SQLite.

- Avoid SQL injection attacks (Parameterized queries, Input sanitization).
- Break down and confirm, server side, any payment amount; reject client submitted prices.

D. Scope

It includes functionality for core member actions (register, log in, view plans and subscribe) along with admin actions (manage plans, process refund). There are still some future work left, including CSRF protection, advanced session management and full RBAC.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

Today’s fitness centers are using the web for membership enroll, payments and exercise courses. They are appealing targets because of the valuable information they carry, including sensitive data or personal and financial information. Completely developed using the principles of SSDLC, FitZone is a Python-Flask application on top of a SQLite database with Stripe test integration.

B. Problem Statement

Gym Management Software with no in-built security measures are open to brute force login attacks, SQL injection, client-side price manipulation, refund fraud, IDOR and session hijacking, putting members’ data at risk as well as the financial systems.

C. Objectives

- Design a centralised, secure platform following SSDLC principles.
- Apply “defense in-depth,” multiple independent security controls.
- Implement robust password management policies and server-side hashing of passwords.

II. REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

A. Functional Requirements

TABLE I
FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

FR-ID	UC	Requirement
FR-01	UC-01	Register with validated personal information.
FR-02	UC-02	Authenticate with secure session management.
FR-03	UC-03	Display membership plans from the database.
FR-04	UC-04	Subscribe with server-side price verification.
FR-05	UC-05	Renew active memberships upon expiry.
FR-06	UC-06	Request a temporary membership freeze.
FR-07	UC-07	Book available fitness sessions.
FR-08	UC-08	View membership status and subscription history.
FR-09	UC-09	Create and manage membership plans (admin).
FR-10	UC-10	Process member refund requests (admin).

B. Security Requirements

TABLE II
SECURITY REQUIREMENTS

ID	Requirement	Status
SR-01	Lock account after 5 failed login attempts.	Implemented
SR-02	Retrieve and verify all payment amounts server-side.	Implemented
SR-03	Use parameterized queries for all DB operations.	Implemented
SR-04	Validate and sanitize all user inputs server-side.	Implemented
SR-05	Store passwords as salted SHA-256 hashes.	Implemented
SR-06	Enforce password policy: 8+ chars, mixed case, digit, special.	Partial
SR-07	Validate CSRF tokens on all state-changing POST requests.	Future
SR-08	Set HttpOnly, Secure, SameSite cookies.	Future
SR-09	Require Multi-Factor Authentication for login.	Future
SR-10	Restrict admin operations to authorised roles (RBAC).	Future

B. Identified Use Cases

TABLE III
SYSTEM USE CASES

ID	Use Case	Status
UC-01	Register Account	Implemented
UC-02	Login	Implemented
UC-03	View Membership Plans	Implemented
UC-04	Purchase Membership	Implemented
UC-05	Renew Membership	Not Implemented
UC-06	Freeze Membership	Not Implemented
UC-07	Book Fitness Session	Not Implemented
UC-08	View Membership Status	Partial
UC-09	Manage Membership Plans	Not Implemented
UC-10	Process Refund Request	Not Implemented

C. Non-Functional Requirements

The system shall respond in less than 2 seconds to a regular load, provide an intuitive user interface, aim for a 99% availability and make use of a modular design for future expansion.

C. Misuse Cases & Diagram

III. USE CASE & MISUSE CASE MODELING

A. Use Case Diagram

Fig. 1. Use case diagram: system actors and functional use cases.

TABLE IV
MISUSE CASES

ID	Misuse Case	Actor	Threat
MUC-01	Unauthorised Access	Ext. Attacker	Brute-force / credential stuffing.
MUC-02	Payment Manipulation	Mal. User	Modify payment params client-side.
MUC-03	SQL Injection	Ext. Attacker	Inject SQL via form fields.
MUC-04	Refund Fraud	Fraud. Member	Exploit refund mechanisms.
MUC-05	Credential Stuffing	Ext. Attacker	Automated login w/ leaked creds.
MUC-06	Session Hijacking	Ext. Attacker	Steal cookies to impersonate user.

Fig. 2. Misuse case diagram: threats and impact on system functionality.

D. Mitigation Controls

TABLE V
MITIGATION CONTROLS

ID	Mitigation	Mitigates	Status
MIT-01	Account Lockout & Rate Limiting	MUC-01	Implemented
MIT-02	Server-Side Payment Validation	MUC-02	Implemented
MIT-03	Input Validation & Param. Queries	MUC-03	Implemented
MIT-04	Refund Policy & Audit Logging	MUC-04	Design only
MIT-05	Multi-Factor Authentication	MUC-01, 05	Design only
MIT-06	Role-Based Access Control	MUC-04	Design only
MIT-07	Secure Session Management	MUC-06	Design only

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. System Architecture

FitZone utilizes a 3-tiered web architecture:

- **Presentation Layer:** Displays HTML/CSS via the browser; validation from the client-side is purely UX and therefore not trusted.
- **Application Layer:** The Python/Flask application enforces all aspects of security controls, performs all validation and session management on the server, and contains all the business logic.

- **Data Layer:** All data is stored using SQLite with all queries to the database being performed with only parameterized statements.

B. UI Prototype Highlights

Fig. 3. UC-02: Login screen showing the attempt counter at 3/5 with lockout warning (MIT-01).

Fig. 4. UC-04: Purchase Membership screen; prices are server-locked before checkout (MIT-02).

C. Database Design

The FitZone database contains 10 entities fully support security requirements including audit logging and role separation. Key entities: **Member** (failed_attempts, is_locked); **Membership_Plan** (authoritative price field); **Subscription**; **Payment_Transaction** (Stripe IDs); **Refund_Request**; **Audit_Log**.

Fig. 5. Entity Relationship Diagram: 10 entities supporting all security and functional requirements.

V. SECURITY DESIGN & CONTROLS

A. Authentication & Session Management

There are no plain text passwords stored; instead there are hash values for passwords based on the SHA-256 hashing algorithm. All authentication is done with Flask server-side sessions. Immediate future work under MIT-07 will be related to advanced session management features such as expiration, HttpOnly/Secure cookie attributes, etc.

B. MIT-01: Account Lockout & Rate Limiting

The Member entity `failed_attempts` are counted by the system. After 5 consecutive failures, `is_locked` is set to `True` and there will be no login. Access is restored upon passing a one-time Unlock Link that will be provided via email. The UI shows a countdown (in 5 dots) and signals a warning when ≤ 2 attempts remain until lockout.

C. MIT-02: Server-Side Payment Validation

Plan price is received solely from the `Membership_Plan` table associated with their `plan_id` provided by the client, and can never be passed from the client. A Price is derived

from this value using a Stripe `PaymentIntent`. Any input or tampering by the client is ignored, and the amount of money displayed on the checkout page will be equal to the amount of money returned by the server.

D. MIT-03: Input Validation & Parameterized Queries

Validation is performed on the server-side for input, and input is checked against a defined format for validation. All queries are executed using parameterized statements through Flask-SQLAlchemy, such that no concatenation occurs with user input in SQL queries.

E. MIT-04 through MIT-07: Designed Controls

- MIT-04: Refund Policy, Audit Trails (MUC-04).
- MIT-05: Implementation of Multi-Factor Authentication (MUC-01, 05).
- MIT-06: Implementation of Role-Based Access Controls (RBAC) (MUC-04).
- MIT-07: Secure Session Management (HttpOnly, Secure, SameSite Cookies) (MUC-06).

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Technology Stack

TABLE VI
TECHNOLOGY STACK

Component	Technology
Frontend	HTML, CSS3
Backend	Python 3, Flask
Database	SQLite
Password Hashing	SHA-256
Payment Gateway	Stripe (test mode)
Security Testing	Manual black-box, Browser Dev-Tools

B. Implemented Modules

Four modules were implemented and tested:

- MIT-01: Account Lockout & Rate Limiting
- UC-02: Member Login
- UC-04: Purchase Membership
- MIT-02: Server-Side Payment Validation

1) *Login & Account Lockout (Module 1)*: Progressive Lockout for Logins is enforced. Accounts are locked after 5 consecutive failures. The dot counter is updated in real-time, warnings are displayed for ≤ 2 remaining attempts, and passwords are hashed using SHA-256.

2) *Payment Validation (Module 2)*: The client does not send any details about the price, only the `plan_id`. The server fetches the verified price from the database, uses that price to create a Stripe `PaymentIntent`, and ignores any price manipulation that may have occurred on the client side.

C. Key Implementation Screenshots

Fig. 6. MIT-01: Account locked after 5 consecutive failed login attempts; unlock email dispatched.

Fig. 7. UC-04: Membership purchased successfully via Stripe after server-side price validation.

VII. TESTING

A. Approach & Environment

Google Chrome, Python/Flask, and SQLite were used for local black box testing. Testing was done using Stripe test mode with the following credit card numbers:

- 4242 4242 4242 4242 — Success
- 4000 0000 0000 0002 — Declined

To test using browsers, the DevTools were used to intercept HTTP Requests and manipulate the payment amounts using ‘Simulate Tamper’, which was built into the software to restore the price.

B. UC-02 & MIT-01: Login & Lockout (TC-01–TC-10)

TABLE VII
TEST CASES: LOGIN & ACCOUNT LOCKOUT

TC#	Test Case	Expected Result	Pass
TC-01	Valid login	Dashboard; session created.	✓
TC-02	Wrong pwd (1st)	Error; 1 dot lit; 4 remaining.	✓
TC-03	Wrong pwd (3rd)	Warning: 2 attempts remaining.	✓
TC-04	Wrong pwd (4th)	Warning: 1 attempt remaining.	✓
TC-05	Locked at 5th	Account locked; all dots red.	✓
TC-06	Login while locked	Error: Account locked; access denied.	✓
TC-07	Empty username	Error: Please enter both fields.	✓
TC-08	Unknown username	Generic: Invalid username or password.	✓
TC-09	Unlock then login	Account unlocked; login succeeds.	✓
TC-10	Correct pwd resets	failed_attempts reset to 0.	✓

C. UC-04 & MIT-02: Purchase & Payment (TC-11–TC-20)

TABLE VIII
TEST CASES: PURCHASE & PAYMENT VALIDATION

TC#	Test Case	Expected Result	Pass
TC-11	Select Gold plan	Lock badge: PLN-002 / SAR 199.	✓
TC-12	Select Silver plan	Lock badge: PLN-001 / SAR 99.	✓
TC-13	Select Platinum plan	Lock badge: PLN-003 / SAR 349.	✓
TC-14	Client price ignored	Server charges SAR 199; price=1 ignored.	✓
TC-15	DOM tamper	Price reverts after 2.5s; alert shown.	✓
TC-16	Valid Stripe payment	Membership activated; Stripe confirms.	✓
TC-17	Declined card	Error: Card declined; plan not activated.	✓
TC-18	Invalid plan ID	Error 400: Invalid plan.	✓
TC-19	Purchase w/o login	Error 401: Not logged in.	✓
TC-20	Price matches DB	Response: Platinum; amount=349.	✓

D. Results Summary

TABLE IX
TEST RESULTS SUMMARY

Module	TCs	Pass	Fail	Rate
UC-02 & MIT-01 (Login & Lockout)	10	10	0	100%
UC-04 & MIT-02 (Purchase & Payment)	10	10	0	100%
Total	20	20	0	100%

MIT-01 Findings: The trigger for lockout occurs after exactly 5 unsuccessful attempts. Feedback through the dot

counter and warning alerts is correctly implemented. Access to the Unlock Mechanism resets the counter and allows normal login.

MIT-02 Findings: In TC-14 (Client submitted price = 1), the charging price was SAR 199. TC-15 confirmed the ability of DOM Tamper Simulation to initiate the Automatic Price Restore Process after approximately 2.5 seconds.

VIII. CONCLUSION

FitZone Gym Membership Management System is an example of how security and functionality can be fully integrated from the beginning, using the SSDLC. 100% of test cases were successful, validating MIT-01 (brute-force prevention) and MIT-02 (payment integrity).

Key lessons:

- Security needs to be thought of from the beginning.
- Certain requirements will make it possible to test security.
- After every security test, test the database to see how it has been impacted as a tangible assessment of the effectiveness of the security.
- Security testing requires thinking like an attacker — what are the vulnerabilities that the functionality testing isn't looking for?

Future work entails Two-Factor Authentication, complete RBAC, CSRF protection, secure session management from MIT-04 to MIT-07, mobile deployment, and real-time anomaly monitoring.

APPENDIX

TABLE X
SECURITY REQUIREMENTS TRACEABILITY MATRIX

SR	Misuse Case	Mitigation	TC(s)	OWASP	Status
SR-05	MUC-01 Brute Force	SHA-256 Hash	TC01, 09	A07	Implemented
SR-06	MUC-01 Weak Pwd	Password Policy	Client only	A07	Partial
SR-02	MUC-02 Price Manip.	MIT-02 Validation	TC14, 15	A01	Implemented
SR-03	MUC-03 SQL Injection	MIT-03 Param. Qry	Code rev.	A03	Implemented
SR-01	MUC-01 Brute Force	MIT-01 Lockout	TC05, 06	A07	Implemented
SR-04	MUC-04 Refund Fraud	MIT-04 Audit Log	—	A09	Future
SR-10	MUC-05 IDOR	Object-Level Auth	—	A01	Future
SR-09	MUC-06 CSRF	CSRF Token	—	A01	Future

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